

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
Grant Agreement No. 101016503

Public Report on ISW Exploitation Results

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Table of contents

1	Summary	3
2	Scope and outline.....	4
3	Introduction to In Silico World	5
3.1	General project objectives	6
3.2	Main barriers to the uptake of In Silico Trials	6
4	Medical Simulation – Market Analysis	8
4.1	Industry Overview.....	8
4.1.1	Digital Twin for Healthcare	8
4.1.2	Translational Precision Medicine.....	8
4.1.3	Healthcare simulation platforms	9
4.2	Market Overview, Dynamics, and Opportunities	9
4.2.1	Patient safety.....	9
4.2.2	Growing geriatric population.....	9
4.2.3	Simulation-based training.....	10
4.2.4	Shortage in healthcare workforce	10
4.3	Competitive landscape	10
5	Intellectual Property Rights and Management.....	11
5.1	Horizon IP Scan	11
5.2	IPR Management Table	12
6	Impact	13

1 Summary

Wherever we look in the healthcare industry, we can find new technologies being used to fight illness, develop new therapies and medical products, and help people live healthier lives. This is also the case of In Silico World, whose aim is accelerating the uptake of modelling and simulation technologies by developing innovative solutions for the development and regulatory assessment of medicines and medical devices,

Exploitation is a crucial activity of ISW as it connects the results of the project to their subsequent market commercialization, aiming to a broader reach to pharmaceutical and medical device industry, healthcare professionals and clinical societies, patients and their families, and other stakeholders involved.

This public report was prepared describing the various exploitation activities performed in ISW project, focusing on the development of a business framework for the commercialization of computational solution to maximize their sustainability and socioeconomic impact. The report contains an overview of the medical simulations market, and for each computational solution within the project, the potential business contexts-of-use was analyzed, in terms of technical features and indication of target users, the envisioned market, and steps towards commercialization, depending on the maturity level reached.

This document is intended to stimulate, encourage, and facilitate project partners' efforts in the exploitation activities of the main findings and outputs arising from the ISW project.

2 Scope and outline

Exploitation is a crucial activity as it connects the results of the project to their subsequent market exploitation. In this document, the exploitation plan of the ISW project is presented and where applicable illustrated with exploitation results already achieved by the end of the project in December 2024.

The 11 ISW solutions developed in the ISW project started with very different levels of Technology Readiness Level (TRL), but after the project they all aim to travel towards industrial exploitation. For some solutions the starting TRL level was rather low, resulting in preliminary and temporary exploitations plans that eventually need to be updated after the end of the project when commercialization is more likely.

For the ISW project, the TRL mapping was done using a domain-specific declination of the standard definition of TRL developed by the Insigneo Institute, as shown in Table 1:

TRL	Description of research and development activities
TRL1: Technical watch	Monitoring of fundamental technological innovations and discovery of fundamental biological mechanisms
TRL2: Basic technology research	Application of fundamental technological innovation to the quantification, prediction, and modification of fundamental biological mechanisms
TRL3: Research to prove feasibility	Demonstration of hypothesis testing and initial proof of concept in a limited number of in silico and in vitro models
TRL4: Technology demonstration	Demonstration of proof of concept and safety in a defined laboratory or animal model
TRL5: Technology demonstration	Preclinical studies, including good laboratory practices, animal safety and toxicity, are sufficient to support industrial application
TRL6: Technology demonstration	Phase 1 clinical trials: support to proceed to Phase 2 clinical trials; safety, usability, impact, accuracy on small cohort
TRL7: System/subsystem development	Phase 2 clinical trials: accuracy and efficacy on medium cohort; scalability and impact
TRL8: System test, launch, and operations	Phase 3 clinical trials: efficacy on large cohort; cost–benefit analysis, primary research for Health Technology Assessment
TRL9: Postmarketing studies and surveillance	Postmarketing studies and surveillance; registers, failure analysis, postmortem examinations

Table 1 - Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) based on Viceconti et al. 2016 (<https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/10.1146/annurev-bioeng-110915-114742>)

For each tool developed within the project, a business model was defined, including the business strategy and its specific characteristic. For some solutions the starting TRL level was rather low, resulting in preliminary and temporary exploitations plans that eventually need to be updated after the end of the project when commercialization is more likely.

3 Introduction to In Silico World

Every new product that enters the market needs to be developed first. In addition, if such a product could be a hazard for human health, the product must undergo an extensive risk assessment, which in most countries and for most class of hazardous products is regulated by law. The use of modelling and simulation to develop and derisk new products is nowadays pervasive, in almost all industrial sectors. For example, a 2012 report by Goldbeck Consulting suggests that only in the chemical industry modelling and simulation brings a gross value added of £13bn (roughly 1% of the UK Gross Domestic Product) and supports 300,000 jobs. Such role can only expand in the near future: in a 2018 report, McKinsey Consulting suggests that Artificial Intelligence (AI) could increase the global economic activity of \$13 trillion by 2030, or about 16 percent higher cumulative GDP compared with today. If we assume that analytic AI, where AI is used for modelling and simulation, is only 25% of this growth we are still in excess of \$3 trillion.

Healthcare is one of the few industrial sectors that has been historically refractory to the use of modelling and simulation in its products developments and derisking. Until 2016, neither the USA Food and Drugs Administration (FDA) nor the European Medicine Agency (EMA) allowed to produce any primary evidence in the regulatory process that was obtained through computer simulation, with only two notable exceptions, that we will discuss in detail in a following section. Also, the product development within companies relied on modelling and simulation in a fairly limited way. The two main justifications commonly provided for this scarce adoption were that the human body was way too complex to be modelled, and that for most physiological and pathological processes of interest we lacked the type of causal, quantitative knowledge required to build mechanistic computer models.

But starting from the early 2000, first with the Physiome Project, and then with the EU-led Virtual Physiological Human (VPH) initiative, researchers all around the world started to develop models able to predict changes in the health status of an individual patient. Initially the target was mostly what is now called Digital Patient or Digital Twin technologies, where the patient-specific model is used to decide the best course of action for that patient, supporting the medical decision. These early research activities showed that in many cases there was indeed enough knowledge to build accurate models, and that the resulting complexity could be tamed with the flexibility of modern modelling technologies, and the huge computational power now available [PMID: 27420570].

But while the first digital patient technologies reached the market (e.g. [PMID: 24486266; PMID: 23611712; PMID: 29665068]) the use of modelling and simulation in the development and derisking of medical products remained limited. In 2013 the FP7 Support Action Avicenna (“A Strategy for In silico Clinical Trials”) early consensus document highlighted that the main perceived barrier to adoption, was the lack of acceptance from the regulatory agencies. Driven by the Avicenna action and by the US Medical Device Innovation Consortium (MDIC) the community of practice formed by academic, industrial, and clinical experts drove a public policy initiative the culminated on 10 March 2016, when the European Parliament through an overwhelming majority, voted in favour of requiring the EMA to take into account alternative models in clinical trials (COM(2014)0557). A similar recommendation was made the same year by the US Congress to FDA (Appropriations Bill S. 1800. [Report No. 114–82]).

Today, nearly eight years after this historical event, the level of uptake of In Silico Trials (IST), e.g., the use of modelling & simulation for the development and derisking of new medical products, is still fairly limited. This suggests that additional barriers are slowing down the rapid uptake.

3.1 General project objectives

The aim of the ISW project is accelerate the uptake of modelling and simulation technologies for the development and regulatory assessment of medicines and medical devices (hereinafter referred generically as in silico trials technologies), by developing innovative solutions that address the main barriers to their uptake. Ultimately, we expect ISW results to accelerate the adoption of in silico trials, increase the trust in these innovative technologies by the main stakeholders, change the design of regulatory trials to include in silico technologies, and consolidate the regulatory pathways based on in silico trials. The long-term impact will be the reduction of the costs and duration of the development a regulatory assessment of new medical products, while maintaining or improving the level of safety provided by conventional approaches. We also expect to change the process in ways that will allow for the first time to learn from failures, providing a causal explanation to the lack of safeness or of effectiveness of the new product, which hopefully can guide to some redevelopment rather than restarting from scratch, as we do nowadays.

To move from these generic objectives to more specific project goals, we need to first articulate with greater detail what we believe are the main barriers to uptake, and then the clinical context within which the project will develop its goals.

3.2 Main barriers to the uptake of In Silico Trials

The call for proposals already indicates some of the most important barriers to adoption. The Avicenna Roadmap listed seven barriers, that at the time of its publication (2016) had been found the most important through a formal consensus process that involved over 600 stakeholders worldwide. Some interesting philosophical perspectives were obtained from a special issue of HUMANA.MENTE Journal of Philosophical Studies (Vol 9 No 30 (2016)), entitled “In Silico Modelling: the Human Factor”. The economic and industrial perspective was taken into account, especially through a number of articles and reports from market analysts, especially from Price Waterhouse & Cooper (PWC), and Deloitte that discuss the barrier to adoption in the testing of medical products of digital technologies in general. Social and ethical elements were derived from an Insigneo report on Responsible research and innovation in in silico medicine. The regulatory landscape was informed by a recent white paper of the Avicenna Alliance.

From these and many other sources the ISW consortium proposes that the primary barriers that are currently preventing a faster uptake of In Silico Trials, are:

- **Better models:** Availability of predictive models advanced and robust enough to aspire a use in the reduction, refinement or replacement of the clinical trials required for the certification of new medical products; challenges to support development; From black box to white box and back.
- **Validation collections:** Lack of widely available collections of curated medical data specifically designed for the development (e.g. for Analytic AI predictors) and the validation of In Silico Trials technologies.

- **Technical Standards:** Extension of the credibility assessment proposed in the ASME VV-40 to models used to evaluate pharmaceutical and combinatory products, and harmonization of the VV-40 in the CEN standardization framework.
- **Regulatory barriers:** “First in kind” qualification of In Silico Trials methods for the evaluation of drugs with EMA. Exploration of new regulatory pathways for class III medical devices and pharmaceutical products that allow a significant reduction of human experimentation with In Silico Trials technologies, and the adoption of a rigorous post-marketing surveillance that monitor the validity of the in silico predictions as the new product is adopted.
- **Risk-benefit analysis and information:** Correct and effective information of all stakeholders (policy makers, patients, doctors, regulators, payers, CROs, technology providers, executives of biomedical companies, etc.) on the opportunities and the risks associated with the use of In Silico Trials technologies. Development and application of a rigorous risk-benefit evaluation framework to assess the adoption of IST technologies, from the perspective of each stakeholder.
- **Scalability:** Scalability and efficient computing of large-scale population models.
- **Training and retraining:** Training and re-training of personnel with the necessary technical skills on IST, to work in industry, regulatory agencies, research hospitals, etc.

4 Medical Simulation – Market Analysis

Medical simulation refers to the simulation of complicated biomechanical and physiological processes to support medical procedures. Through medical simulation, physicians, surgeons, medical professionals, and medical product producers may have access to previously untapped knowledge that they may incorporate into product creation, diagnosis, and therapy for patients' benefit.

Medical device and drug manufacturers are always required to demonstrate a product's efficacy and safety in a physiological and pathological range of a target population. This is accomplished by rigorous and lengthy trials and clinical testing on thousands of probands. If a medical device fails at this stage, the financial losses might be devastating, and the product does not reach the market. Medical simulation and in silico clinical trials can be designed and conducted on virtual patients faster utilizing medical simulation, with no risk to subjects and lower risks and costs for manufacturers.

Medical simulation encourages cross-domain ideas and ways to extend and sustainably improve existing processes or process chains; as a result, more and newer therapeutic options arise.

4.1 Industry Overview

Modelling and simulation (in silico) techniques allow to replicate and reproduce complex biomechanical and physiological processes, in order to support the development or regulatory evaluation of new medical products, devices or treatments. Through medical simulations, physicians, surgeons, medical professionals, and medical device producers have access to previously untapped knowledge that they may incorporate into product creation, diagnosis, and therapy for patients' benefit. Medical simulation encourages cross-domain ideas and ways to extend and sustainably improve existing processes or process chains; as a result, more and newer therapeutic options arise.

4.1.1 Digital Twin for Healthcare

Digital twins are digital representations of human physiology built on computer models, in which data relating to both the individual and the population are introduced. Technological advances are accelerating the creation of these digital twins, which underlie data-driven models capable of preventing, diagnosing, and treating diseases.

The use of digital twins in healthcare is revolutionizing clinical processes and hospital management by enhancing medical care with digital tracking and advancing the modelling of the human body. These tools may represent great help to researchers in studying diseases, new drugs and medical devices and may also help physicians optimize the performance of patient-specific treatment plans.

In the short term, digital twins will help the healthcare system in bringing life-saving innovations to market faster, at lower costs and with greater safety for the patient. The key to translating digital twins' value into real impact lies in large-scale implementation: making the technology widely accessible in the clinical routine, innovating key clinical processes using digital simulations, and improving medical care.

4.1.2 Translational Precision Medicine.

Drug discovery and development now have unprecedented opportunities for new product and business model innovation, fundamentally altering the conventional approach to how drugs are discovered, developed, and marketed. This is especially true in the age of precision medicine, digital technologies, and artificial

intelligence. Digital biomarkers, model-based data integration, artificial intelligence, biomarker-guided trial designs, and patient-centred companion diagnostics are important elements of translational precision medicine.

4.1.3 Healthcare simulation platforms

Digital platforms are transforming healthcare, with healthcare platforms set to become part of the 'new normal'. Medicine is evolving, and with the aid of in silico medical simulation, it has the potential to play a significant role in clinical practice.

Today healthcare simulation (platforms) can help companies by reducing time and costs required by R&D process, as well as subsequent registration / certification processes of new drugs, medical devices and treatments. Though regulatory agencies are recommending companies to adopt these practices, many small and medium-sized biotech organizations may lack the expensive hardware infrastructure and simulation software required, and high expertise needed to develop and use models.

4.2 *Market Overview, Dynamics, and Opportunities*

The global medical simulation market size was estimated at USD 1.72 billion in 2020 and is expected to expand at a CAGR of 16.3% from 2021 to 2028¹. Growing technological advancements, preference for minimally invasive treatment, and focus on patient safety are the factors anticipated to boost the market growth. North America held the largest share of medical simulation in 2021 estimated to be around USD 900 million and is expected to expand at a CAGR of 15.8% from 2021 to 2028².

Based on products and services, the market is segmented into web-based simulators, healthcare anatomical models, simulation training services, and healthcare simulation software. The web-based simulation segment is expected to register the highest growth to more than a quarter of the medical simulation market during the forecasted period (2021-2028). Factors responsible for the growth of this segment are the controlled and predictable learning environments and controlled access to simulation procedures.

4.2.1 Patient safety

According to a 2019 study published by the WHO³, about 2.6 million people die every year in low- and middle-income countries due to patient harm in healthcare, making it the 14th leading cause of morbidity and mortality. Most detrimental errors are related to diagnosis and treatments. The rising number of medical errors and the need to ensure patient safety and high-quality care have become key priorities for healthcare organizations worldwide. Hospitals are expected to register the highest growth by end user of medical simulation market, with the increased focus on patient safety and the growing demand for minimally invasive surgeries being the factors attributed to the growth of this segment.

4.2.2 Growing geriatric population

The growing global geriatric population, changing lifestyles, rising prevalence of chronic diseases is expected to keep contributing to the surge in demand computational technologies integrated into healthcare systems

¹ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/simulation-software-market>

² <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/simulation-software-market>

³ <https://www.who.int/news/item/13-09-2019-who-calls-for-urgent-action-to-reduce-patient-harm-in-healthcare>

for early diagnosis, improved understanding, and accurate prediction of diseases in their early stage based on historical health datasets progression in their initial stages⁴.

4.2.3 Simulation-based training

The increased adoption of simulation-based training and certification of upskilling healthcare professionals may represent an efficient means to improve patient safety and outcomes. This would result in a significantly larger addressable market than the current market, which is primarily education based. Training through simulation can help clinicians gain confidence knowledge and expertise for improving patient safety in a risk-free environment⁵.

4.2.4 Shortage in healthcare workforce

The growing shortage of healthcare workforce is expected to drive the adoption of computational technologies to support care providers in quickly diagnosing the condition and devising an accurate treatment regime, reducing machine downtime, and minimizing care expenses. Owing to the Covid-19 pandemic, computational technologies witnessed a significant boost in adoption and are set to experience a dramatic growth trajectory⁶.

4.3 *Competitive landscape*

Today, different digital twin solutions exist in healthcare to support industry and hospitals in the processes of development, planning, regulatory approval and post market surveillance of new treatments. Some of these platforms, like SimQ (simq.de), Novadiscovery's Jinko (www.novadiscovery.com/jinko) and Certara's Phoenix and Simcyp (www.certara.com/software), integrate models from partners or from literature, providing the user with an intuitive interface to setup, run models and visualize results.

Other solutions are not accessible by the user through web-based interfaces and require a higher level of expertise to the user, such as Elem (www.elem.bio), Sim4Life (zmt.swiss/sim4life) and other solvers like Comsol (www.comsol.com), Ansys (www.ansys.com) and Dassault Systèmes' products (www.3ds.com). Dassault Systèmes has also developed the web-based platform 3DEXperience (www.3ds.com/3dexperience).

This list clearly omits all modelling-based consultancy services currently provided by many institutions and research teams with modelling and simulation expertise.

⁴ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/artificial-intelligence-ai-healthcare-market>

⁵ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/medical-healthcare-simulation-market>

⁶ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/artificial-intelligence-ai-healthcare-market>

5 Intellectual Property Rights and Management

Before the start of the project, the Partners have entered a binding Consortium Agreement (CA) based on Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement (DESCA), a comprehensive Model Consortium Agreement offering a reliable frame of reference for project consortia. Its scope is to ensure that each partner can exploit the results in an efficient, fair & equitable manner, to maximize the project impact.

As it covers all aspects of administration, partner relations & responsibilities, the CA also details the Access Rights to Foreground & Background and sets out availability rules for the participant Background needed for the project implementation, including possible limitations of use. As a general principle, Access Rights for the implementation of the project are granted on a royalty-free basis, as the Access rights to Results will be for internal research activities. Access Rights to the Results needed for the exploitation of a party's own results shall be granted on fair and reasonable conditions, as will be the Access Rights to Background whenever similarly needed.

The allocation of IPRs in the consortium is based on the guiding principle in H2020, where the Partners retain the ownership of their respective foreground. For joint efforts, there will be an up-front division of Intellectual Property (IP) ownership among Partners according to core business areas & relative participations to the project deliverables, coupled with the default H2020 joint ownership whenever the respective efforts of the Partners cannot be ascertained directly.

5.1 Horizon IP Scan

During the first half of 2022, partners ISTT and MIM applied and were accepted to participate to Horizon IP Scan⁷, a tailored, free-of-charge, first-line IP support service provided by the European Commission specifically designed to help European start-ups and other SMEs involved in EU-funded collaborative research projects to efficiently manage and valorise IP in collaborative R&I efforts.

Horizon IP Scan entails three major steps:

1. a preparation phase including a pre-interview;
2. the main interview, which is done in an in-person or online meeting;
3. and the provision of a report and recommendations.

The service was delivered by the qualified IP expert SILVIA DONDI. During the main interview, a schematic summary was illustrated to ISTT for better understanding the management of IP within the Project. It was pointed out and remarked that the starting point for the co-operative ISW project is sharing knowledge among the beneficiaries.

At the end of the service, the following main recommendations were provided:

- Ensure the partners involved in the project take the appropriate actions aimed at implementing a secrecy system regulating the treatment of all kinds of information, in particular labelling any confidential information exchanged with other parties as "confidential information".
- Aim at protecting ISW IP results (owned or co-owned), in particular:
 - a. Software by registering the copyright.
 - b. Web interface by registering an industrial design or a copyright.
 - c. Software/Data by creating a strong policy on secrecy measures.

⁷ https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/horizon-ip-scan_en

- d. In the case of joint ownership, negotiations shall be driven by the clauses set up in the CA.
- Since dissemination is a goal of the Project, any conflicts with patentability purposes should be avoided. Dissemination of joint results shall be preceded by a notice given to the other co-owners at least 15 calendar days before publication, bearing in mind to carefully examine the material to be published and to raise any objection in due time.
 - Attention shall be drawn to implementing a policy on trade secrets and to deciding the best IP right on a case-by-case basis.
 - FTO search on an international database is highly recommended for assessing whether the final products may be actuated is highly recommended. The FTO may also be updated later, before the launch on the market.

5.2 IPR Management Table

WP8 partner has organized periodic meetings with each solution developer, to collect and update all information necessary for definition and management of intellectual property rights, and in particular to identify potential obstacles to commercial exploitation.

The information collected covers:

- Solution type and description,
- Description and ownership and any constraints related to Background IP,
- Description and ownership and any constraints related of the Foreground IP,
- Identification of potential constraints to exploitation (third party components, previous license transfers, only research use, limited distribution, pending patents, ...),
- IP protection strategy identified (trade secret, software copyright, industrial design, patent, computer implemented inventions, ...)
- Additional steps required before exploitation (support, maintenance, further development...),
- Potential direct exploitation (commercialisation, contract research, funded research project, education/training, ...)
- Potential indirect exploitation (assignment/transfer of the IPR, licensing of the IPR, development of a new legislation/standard, Spin-off, ...)

The IPR Management Table has been further updated at the end of the project at M48. No critical situations have been identified that may endanger the potential commercial exploitation of the various solutions.

6 Impact

As described in section 2.1 of the project proposal, the ISW consortium describes a preliminary exploitation strategy for the results produced during the project. This strategy is grounded by a set of 12 specific KPIs. During the project, some modifications have been proposed in the light of the results obtained so far, with indication of the corrective actions.

We originally proposed that, once this project is completed, the time to validate, certify, and deploy an IST solution would be around 3 years (KPI01). We also proposed that, once this project is completed, the number of alternative regulatory pathways deployed would increase to 2 (KPI03), and the number of qualification advice received would increase to 3 (KPI04). While for medical devices we can confirm our rather optimistic projection, caution is required for medicinal products. The severity of the scrutiny we faced in the first qualification advice (BBCT-hip) suggests that the role of IST for drugs will be limited at least for some time to the support of pre-clinical studies and of reduction, refinement and replacement of animal experimentation. The two qualification advice procedures with EMA are now both completed (BBCT-hip and UISS-TB). An extensive report, summarising and analysing the consortium's work concerning the regulatory barriers and draws some recommendations for EU policymakers, was published on April 9, 2024, on the Zenodo ISW community⁸. On the date of 13 December 2024, it has collected 555 views and 287 downloads.

Related to contributing to setting standards for computer modelling solutions for testing, under the initiative of the In Silico World project, a joint International Electrotechnical Commission- International Organization for Standardization (IEC-ISO) workgroup has been established in liaison with the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) VV-40 committee, with the goal of developing an international equivalent to the ASME VV-40 technical standard on “Assessing Credibility of Computational Modeling through Verification and Validation: Application to Medical Devices”. Moreover, the Open Access book “Toward Good Simulation Practice - Best practices for the use of computational modelling & simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products”⁹ was published by Springer Nature on 23 February 2024. This consensus document, with a foreword by United States Food and Drug Administration (US FDA) regulator, represents the first attempt to produce a consensus position on the best practice for In Silico Trials. On the date of 13 December 2024, the book has collected more than 35k accessed/downloads, and 2 citations.

Finally, we proposed to modify the definition of KPI12 considering recent developments. All our data and information resources (such as validation collections) are being already shared through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), on the Zenodo ISW Community. However, our In Silico Trials solutions will most likely be shared through the new European Infrastructure dedicated to the Virtual Human Twin¹⁰. The European Commission (EC) officially launched the programme in December 2023 with an event and the publication of a manifesto¹¹. A European tender for the development of the “Platform for Advanced Virtual Human Twin (VHT) Models”¹² was launched on 16 April and 2024 and closed on 7 June 2024, with several ISW partners participating in tender teams; results are still pending. Since such infrastructure has not been officially defined yet, we propose to reformulate KPI12 as “Solutions exposed via EU infrastructures”.

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/10948478>

⁹ [Toward Good Simulation Practice: Best practices for the use of computational modelling & simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products | SpringerLink](https://www.springer.com/9789811984444)

¹⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/virtual-human-twins>

¹¹ <https://www.virtualhumantwins.eu/>

¹² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/funding/platform-advanced-virtual-human-twin-vht-models>

Table 2 – Monitoring of ISW KPIs at M48.

KPI#	KPI Definition	Aspect to impact	Means of verification	UoM	Initial value	Target value	Revision at M18	Revision at M36	Revision at M48
KPI01	Time to validate, certify, and deploy an IST solution	Accelerate adoption	Monitor times for ISW solutions	Years	NA	3yr	3yrs for Med Dev > 5yrs for Drugs	3yrs for Med Dev > 5yrs for Drugs	3yrs for Med Dev > 5yrs for Drugs
KPI02	Change in perception across stakeholders	Increase users trust	Questionnaires to stakeholder groups before and after targeted communication	%	Baseline	>50%	>50%	>50%	>50%
KPI03	Number of alternative regulatory pathways deployed	Redesign clinical trials	Count pathways qualified by regulators	Num.	0	2	<u>1</u>	<u>1</u>	<u>1</u>
KPI04	Number of qualification advices received	Engage regulators	Count QA received	Num.	0	3	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>
KPI05	Estimated reduction of animals in CT	Reduce human/animal exp.	Average reduction as calculated for each context of use of relevant ISW solutions	%	Baseline	>30%	>30%	>30%	>30%
KPI06	Estimated reduction of humans in CT	Reduce human/animal exp.	Average reduction as calculated for each context of use of relevant ISW solutions	%	Baseline	>20%	>20% for Med Dev unlikely for drugs	>20% for Med Dev unlikely for drugs	>20% for Med Dev unlikely for drugs
KPI07	Estimated probability of adverse event for MedDev	Increase safety/efficacy	Maximum cohort size (physical + virtual) on which the device can be tested	%	1%	0.10%	0.10%	0.10%	0.10%
KPI08	Estimated probability of adverse event for ATMPs	Increase safety/efficacy	Maximum cohort size (physical + virtual) on which the ATMP can be tested	%	1%	0.10%	0.10%	0.10%	0.10%
KPI09	Estimated benefit of adopting ISW for drugs / ATMPs	Reduce cost to market	Average reduction as calculated for each context of use of relevant ISW solutions	Euro	€2.4B	<€2B	<€2B	<€2B	<€2B
KPI10	Estimated benefit of adopting ISW for MedDev	Reduce cost to market	Average reduction as calculated for each context of use of relevant ISW solutions	Euro	€100M	80M	80M	80M	80M
KPI11	Policy documents on standardisation	Setting Standards	Number of standardisation recommendations produced	Num.	0	1	1	<u>2</u>	<u>2</u>
KPI12	Solutions exposed via EOSC/EDI EU Infrastructures	Contribute to ECI (European Cloud Initiative)	Number of solutions exposed	Num.	0	2	2	3	3